

How to play

Roll a dice and move forward depending on the action you will find. When you land on the accessibility symbol, pick an action card.

Put the action cards here.

Meet **Lulù**, a passionate climate activist dedicated to organising events that promote awareness of climate change. She is focused on making these events and their communication accessible to everyone. She needs your support. Help her!

Great colour contrast on the poster! Move 1 space!

START

Finish!

ActionCards

Cut and place the action cards on the board.

Create an **accessible hashtag** for a climate change-related event.

List **five solutions** to make your event accessible to everyone.

Self describe yourself and your current surroundings.

Take a picture and try writing **the alternative text** for it.

Look around and **find two accessibility features** where you are.

What is Braille?
Explain it to the other players.

ActionCards

Cut and place the action cards on the board.

Sign your name!
(Or nickname)

Look around! What **accessibility barriers** can you find?

What is an accessibility barrier?
Explain it to the other players.

What is Easy Language? Explain it to the other players.

Think **two situations in which you might need subtitles.**

Think one situation in which you might need **audio description.**

LULÚ, THE COMMUNICATION BARRIER BREAKER

Objective of the game

The goal of the game is to help **Lulú**, a climate activist, organise events that are accessible and inclusive, with the aim of raising awareness about climate change.

Game materials

- Game board
 - Action cards
 - Player tokens (one for each player)
 - Dice
 - Instructions
 - [Climate Advocacy Toolkit](#) as a reference guide
 - Extra game board and action cards for customisation.
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Setup

1. Place the game board on a flat surface.
 2. Each player places their token on the starting line.
 3. Shuffle the action cards and place them in a deck next to the board.
 4. Players roll the dice to determine the playing order (the player who rolls the highest number starts).
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How to play

1. Rolling and moving

- Each player rolls the dice and moves their token forward by the number shown on the dice.

2. Types of spaces

○ Accessibility spaces

Landing on a space that highlights good accessibility practices (e.g., providing subtitles, using a wheelchair ramp) allows the player to move forward the number of spaces indicated. This rewards them for promoting accessibility.

- **Penalty spaces**
If the player lands on a space indicating a lack of accessibility (e.g., an event without accessible restrooms or no sign language interpreter), they must move back the number of spaces indicated as a penalty or miss a turn.
 - **Action spaces**
When a player lands on an action space, they must draw an action card and complete the task provided (e.g., "List five solutions to make your event accessible to everyone").
 - If the player cannot successfully complete the action, they miss a turn. The trainer helps players understand the action cards and adapt them as needed (Refer to the Trainer's role section).
 - **Emergency exit spaces**
When a player lands on an emergency exit space, they can travel to the next emergency exit space on the board.
 - If the exit sign points to the right, move forward to the next exit space.
 - If the exit sign points to the left, move backward to the previous exit space.
 - Note: Emergency exits are special spaces that must be followed regardless of how you reach them. Whether you land on an emergency exit while moving forward, backward due to a penalty, or after completing a challenge or receiving a reward, you must follow the exit's direction.
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Trainer's role

The trainer (or facilitator) plays an essential role in the game. They help explain unfamiliar terms and concepts to players and can use the [Climate Advocacy Toolkit](#) as a reference tool to clarify any doubts. If a player encounters a word or concept they do not understand, the trainer can provide guidance or suggest looking up the information online. Trainers are also encouraged to use the blank version of the game to modify action cards and tailor them to the specific needs of the group.

Action cards

In the game, **Action cards** are a crucial part of the gameplay, introducing challenges that require players to think about and demonstrate their understanding of accessibility in different contexts. These cards provide tasks, questions, or scenarios that players must respond to, adding a layer of active learning to the game.

Examples:

List five solutions to make your event accessible to everyone: Possible answers might include: providing sign language interpreters, ensuring physical accessibility with ramps, adding captions to videos, offering materials in braille, and making websites screen-reader friendly.

"What is Braille? Explain it to the other players: The player must explain that braille is a tactile writing system used by people who are blind or visually impaired, consisting of raised dots representing letters, numbers, and punctuation.

Create an accessible hashtag for a climate change event: The player must come up with a hashtag using **CamelCase** (capitalising the first letter of each word) to ensure it is easy to read for screen readers, such as #ClimateChangeForEveryone.

Note:

If any words are unfamiliar, players can use the internet to research or ask the trainer for clarification. The trainer can adjust the difficulty of action cards based on the players' understanding.

End of the game

The first player to reach the final space wins the game and is recognised as having successfully helped Lulú organise an accessible and inclusive event.

To reach the goal, the player must land on it using the exact number of moves. If you roll a number higher than the spaces remaining, move forward to the goal, then use the remaining moves to go backward. For example, if you roll a 5 but only have 3 spaces left, move forward 3 spaces to the goal, then move back 2 spaces.

Additional rules

Trainers can customise the game by modifying the action cards (using the blank version provided) and the game board to suit the needs of the group or specific learning objectives.

This game offers a fun and interactive way to learn about accessibility in climate communication. It encourages players to think about how events can be made more

inclusive while providing hands-on experience in overcoming accessibility challenges. Have fun playing and learning with Lulú!

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Clear Climate

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